

Replication Package for: Breaking Echo Chambers: An Experimental Study on the Willingness to Listen to Opposite Views

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Overview

This replication package contains all data and code necessary to replicate the results in "Breaking Echo Chambers: An Experimental Study on the Willingness to Listen to Opposite Views" published in Economic Journal. The package includes data and analysis code for ****four separate surveys****:

1. ****Survey 3****: Main treatment study comparing etiquette vs. universal values appeals
2. ****Survey 4****: Neutral baseline condition (no treatment)
3. ****Survey 5****: Donation validation study
4. ****Survey 6****: Consent/opt-in study

Package Contents

```
replication_package/
├── README.md (this file)
├── LICENSE.txt (data and code licenses)
├── 00_master.do (master file - runs all surveys)
├── data_raw/ (Survey 3 raw data)
│   ├── data.dta
│   └── data.csv
├── data_raw_s4/ (Survey 4 raw data)
│   ├── data.dta
│   └── data.csv
├── data_raw_s5/ (Survey 5 raw data)
│   ├── data.dta
│   └── data.csv
├── data_raw_s6/ (Survey 6 raw data)
│   ├── s6_data.dta
│   └── s6_data.csv
├── data_clean/ (Cleaned datasets - created by code)
│   ├── data_clean.dta (S3)
│   ├── data_clean.csv (S3)
│   ├── data_clean_s4/
│   │   ├── data_clean.dta
│   │   └── data_clean.csv
│   └── data_clean_s5/
```

```

├── data_clean.dta
├── data_clean.csv
├── data_clean_s6/
│   ├── data_clean.dta
│   └── data_clean.csv
├── code/
│   ├── 00_data_cleaning.do           (Survey 3 cleaning)
│   ├── 01_main_analysis.do         (Survey 3 analysis)
│   ├── 00_data_cleaning_S4.do      (Survey 4 cleaning)
│   ├── 01_analysis_S4.do          (Survey 4 analysis)
│   ├── 00_data_cleaning_S5.do      (Survey 5 cleaning)
│   ├── 01_analysis_S5.do          (Survey 5 analysis)
│   ├── 00_data_cleaning_S6.do      (Survey 6 cleaning)
│   └── 01_analysis_S6.do          (Survey 6 analysis)
├── output/
│   ├── tables/                     (all regression tables)
│   └── figures/                     (all graphs and figures)
...

```

Data Availability Statement

This paper uses data collected through four Qualtrics and Prolific surveys conducted by the authors between 2022 and 2026.

Survey Descriptions:

****Survey 3 (Main Study, N=2,507):**** Randomized controlled trial testing two treatments (etiquette appeals vs. universal values appeals) on willingness to engage with politically opposing audio content.

****Survey 4 (Neutral Baseline, N=~110):**** Control condition with no treatment, providing baseline engagement rates.

****Survey 5 (Donation Validation, N=100):**** Validates stated political preferences through charitable donation allocation (\$30 split between opposing charities).

****Survey 6 (Willingness to Listen, N=301):**** Tests effect of treatments on ****consent**** to listen (opt-in design vs. automatic presentation in Survey 3).

****Data Access:****

- All de-identified survey data is included in this replication package
- Raw survey responses are available in `data_raw/`, `data_raw_s4/`, `data_raw_s5/`, and `data_raw_s6/`
- Cleaned analysis data is automatically generated by the cleaning scripts

****Ethical Approval:**** This study was approved by Cornell University IRB in June

2021.

****Privacy:**** All personally identifiable information has been removed from the data files.

Statement About Rights

The author(s) of the manuscript certify that:

- a) The author(s) have legitimate access to and permission to use all data in this manuscript.
- b) The author(s) have documented permission to redistribute/publish the data contained within this replication package.
- c) All data in this package has been de-identified and does not contain personally identifiable information.
- d) Appropriate permissions and licenses are documented in the `LICENSE.txt` file.

Computational Requirements

Software Requirements

****Required Software:****

- Stata 18-SE
- Operating System: Windows 10/11, macOS 10.15+, or Linux

****Required Stata Packages**** (all available from SSC):

- `estout` - for regression tables
Installation: `ssc install estout`
- `balancetable` - for balance tables
Installation: `ssc install balancetable`
- `statplot` - for statistical plots
Installation: `ssc install statplot`
- `diff` - for difference-in-differences
Installation: `ssc install diff`
- `byhist` - for histogram by groups
Installation: `ssc install byhist`
- `cleanplots` - for graph schemes
Installation: `net install cleanplots`

```
from("https://tdmize.github.io/data/cleanplots")`
```

```
- `binscatterhist` - for binned scatterplots with histograms  
  Installation: `ssc install binscatterhist`
```

```
- `outreg2` - for exporting tables  
  Installation: `ssc install outreg2`
```

****Package Installation:**** The master file (`00_master.do`) will check for missing packages and provide installation instructions if any are not found.

Hardware Requirements

- ****Memory:**** 4 GB RAM minimum (8 GB recommended)
- ****Storage:**** 1 GB free disk space
- ****Processor:**** Standard desktop or laptop processor

Expected Running Time

****Total running time:**** Approximately 15-20 minutes on a standard desktop computer (Intel Core i5 or equivalent)

- Survey 3: ~5-10 minutes (main analysis)
- Survey 4: ~1-2 minutes (baseline analysis)
- Survey 5: ~1-2 minutes (validation analysis)
- Survey 6: ~1-2 minutes (consent analysis)

Instructions for Replication

Step 1: Setup

1. Download and extract the entire replication package to your local computer
2. Note the path where you extracted the files (e.g.,
`C:/Users/YourName/replication_package`)

Step 2: Configure Paths

1. Open `00_master.do` in Stata
2. Change the global path to your local directory:
````stata  
global root "C:/Users/YourName/replication\_package"  
````
3. Save the file

Step 3: Install Required Packages

If you don't have the required packages installed, run these commands in Stata:

```

```stata
ssc install estout
ssc install balancetable
ssc install statplot
ssc install diff
ssc install byhist
ssc install binscatterhist
ssc install outreg2
net install cleanplots, from("https://tdmize.github.io/data/cleanplots")
```

```

Alternatively, the master file will check for missing packages and notify you.

Step 4: Run the Replication

1. In Stata, run: ``do "C:/Users/YourName/replication_package/00_master.do"```
2. The master file will:
 - Clean all raw data for all four surveys
 - Generate all analysis results for all surveys
 - Save all outputs to ``output/tables/`` and ``output/figures/``

****Note:**** You can also run individual survey analyses by running their specific cleaning and analysis files, but you must set the global paths manually in each file.

Output Files

Survey 3 (Main Treatment Study)

****Main Tables (Paper):****

| File | Description | Location in Paper |
|---------------------------|---|-------------------|
| <code>`table1.tex`</code> | Willingness to engage | Table 1 |
| <code>`table4.tex`</code> | Changes in views and Extremeness of views | Table 4 |

****Appendix Tables:****

| File | Description | Location in Paper |
|---|---|-------------------|
| <code>`tableA6.tex`</code> | Changes in views conditional on priors | Table A6 |
| <code>`tableA7.tex`</code> | Changes in extremeness of views conditional on priors | Table A7 |
| <code>`tableA8.tex`</code> | Changes in views, controlling for which recording a person listened to | Table A8 |
| <code>`tableA9.tex`</code> | Changes in extremeness of views, controlling for which recording person listened to | Table A9 |
| <code>`table4_regby_pre_views.tex`</code> | Neutral vs extreme subgroups | Table A6 |

****Robustness Tables:****

- `tableA2.tex` - Sample characteristics & balance checks
- `tableA4.tex` - WTE by topic
- `tableA5.tex` - WTE by topic and pre-treatment views
- `tableA10.tex` - Time spent on page as fraction of length of recordings, controlling for baseline preferences
- `tableA11.tex` - WTE, controlling for baseline preferences
- `tableA12.tex` - WTE, controlling for socio-economic and demographic characteristics.
- `balance_listeners.xls` - Balance for listeners subset
- table A13 - Sample characteristics & balance checks on the subset of listeners
- table A14 - Changes in extremeness of views -Intensive margin
- table A15 - Changes in extremeness of views, by political p
- table A17 - Willingness to Listen 'After the Survey' - Complementary Study
- table A18 - Motivations for Listening
- table A19 - Motivations for Not Listening

****Figures:****

- Pre-treatment views: `abort_pre.png`, `guns_pre.png`, `immi_pre.png`
- Changes in views: `abort_changes.png`, `guns_changes.png`, `immi_changes.png`
- Before/after histograms: `*_changes_hist.png`
- Values and etiquette distributions
- Audio engagement graphs

Survey 4 (Neutral Baseline)

| File | Description |
|-------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| `table1_neutral_rr.xls` | Baseline engagement without treatment |

Survey 5 (Donation Validation)

| File | Description |
|--------------------------------|--|
| `donations_wholesample_bw.png` | Views vs. charitable donation correlations |
| `abortion_donation.gph` | Abortion views vs. donations |
| `immi_donation.gph` | Immigration views vs. donations |
| `guns_donation.gph` | Gun law views vs. donations |
| `lottery_winners.xlsx` | Winners for actual charitable donations |

Survey 6 (Consent/Opt-in)

| File | Description |
|-------------------------|------------------------------------|
| `pap_outcomes.tex` | All four PAP outcomes combined |
| `agreed_to_listen.tex` | Consent analysis (primary outcome) |
| `wte_5sec.tex` | Listened at least 5 seconds |
| `listened_to_all.tex` | Listened to entire audio |
| `tot_perc_engage_b.tex` | Percentage listened |
| `reasons_listened.doc` | Reasons for agreeing to listen |

```
| `reasons_not_listened.doc` | Reasons for declining to listen |  
| `interactions_consent.tex` | Treatment x score interactions |
```

Other Results not in Output folder

These results are displayed in the Stata console when running the analysis code and are not saved as separate files in the output folder.

****Main Tables:**** Code included in "01_main_analysis.do"

- Table 2 - Views and Extremeness of Views - Before and After Opportunity to Engage
- Table 3 - Change in Views (Absolute values) - Overall and Conditional on Changing Views

****Appendix Tables:****

- Table A1 - Sample characteristics vs U.S. population - Code included in "01_main_analysis.do"
- Table A3 - Engagement Levels - Main Survey VS Baseline Comparison Survey - Code included in "01_analysis_S4.do"
- Table A16 - Relationship between policy preferences and allocation decisions - Code included in "01_main_analysis.do"

Survey-Specific Details

Survey 3: Main Treatment Study

****Design:**** 3-arm randomized controlled trial

- Control: No treatment message
- Treatment 1 (Etiquette): Appeal based on social etiquette norms
- Treatment 2 (Universal Values): Appeal based on universal human values

****Key Outcomes:****

1. Willingness to engage (number of audio files listened to for ≥ 5 seconds)
2. Percentage of audio content consumed
3. Changes in political views (absolute difference pre/post)
4. Changes in firmness of views (distance from midpoint)

****Audio Content:**** 47 audio files on three topics (abortion, immigration, gun laws), balanced for ideological position (pro/anti)

Survey 4: Neutral Baseline

****Design:**** No treatment condition

- Provides baseline engagement rates without any appeal

****Purpose:**** Compare engagement rates with Survey 3 to isolate treatment effects

****Key Outcome:**** Willingness to engage with demographic controls

Survey 5: Donation Validation

****Design:**** Revealed preference validation study

- Participants allocate \$30 between opposing charities on each of 3 topics
- Lottery winners (10%) have their choices implemented as actual donations

****Key Analysis:**** Correlation between stated policy preferences and charitable donation allocations

****Key Findings:**** Strong correlation ($r=0.65-0.87$) validates that stated preferences predict actual behavior

Survey 6: Consent/Opt-in Study

****Design:**** 3-arm RCT with opt-in consent requirement

- Same treatments as Survey 3
- ****Key difference:**** Participants must click "I want to listen" before accessing audio

****Purpose:**** Test whether treatments affect CONSENT to engage (vs. actual engagement conditional on exposure)

****Key Outcomes:****

1. Agreement to listen (consent)
2. Conditional engagement given consent
3. Reasons for agreeing/declining

Variable Definitions

Key Outcome Variables (Survey 3 & 6)

****Willingness to Engage (WTE):****

- `wte_pap` - Number of audio files listened to (0-3), where listening is defined as: (i) listened to at least 5 seconds, AND (ii) self-reported listening to "some of it"
- `tot_perc_engage_b` - Percentage of total audio length listened to (bounded at 100%)

****Changes in Views:****

- `views_diff_[topic]_abs` - Absolute change in views on topic (0-10 scale)
- `changed_views_all_abs` - Sum of absolute changes across all three topics

****Firmness of Views:****

- `[topic]_change_firm` - Change in distance from midpoint (5), measuring change in extremeness

Treatment Variables

- `Tx_group` - Treatment group assignment:
 - 1 = Control
 - 2 = Etiquette treatment
 - 3 = Universal values treatment

Audio Content Classification

Abortion audios:

- Pro-choice: audio6, audio16, audio17, audio20, audio30, audio43, audio46
- Pro-life: audio9, audio10, audio15, audio18, audio19, audio21, audio34, audio36, audio37, audio38

Immigration audios:

- Pro-immigration: audio5, audio7, audio8, audio11, audio24, audio27, audio28, audio29, audio32
- Anti-immigration: audio3, audio13, audio23, audio40

Gun law audios:

- Pro-stricter laws: audio2, audio14, audio22, audio25, audio31, audio33, audio44, audio47
- Anti-stricter laws: audio1, audio4, audio26, audio35, audio39, audio41, audio42, audio45, audio12

Survey-Specific Variables

Survey 5:

- `abortion_pro_donation_perc` - Percentage of \$30 donated to pro-abortion charity
- `immi_pro_donation_perc` - Percentage donated to pro-immigration charity
- `guns_against_donation_perc` - Percentage donated to anti-gun charity

Survey 6:

- `agreed_to_listen` - Clicked "I want to listen" (0/1)
- `why_curious`, `why_new`, `why_common` - Reasons for agreeing
- `why_not_money`, `why_not_familiar`, `why_not_nocommon` - Reasons for declining

Known Issues

1. **Graph schemes:** If the `cleanplots` scheme is not installed, graphs will use Stata's default scheme. Results remain unchanged.
2. **Package versions:** Code was tested with the package versions available as of January 2026. Future package updates may require minor code adjustments.
3. **Table formatting:** LaTeX tables (.tex files) are formatted for use with `estout`. XLS files can be opened in Excel.

4. **Survey 4 intermediate file:** Survey 4 cleaning creates an intermediate file `data2.dta` which must be present for the analysis to run.

5. **Long variable names:** Some variable names in Survey 6 use lowercase naming convention (e.g., `timer_audio1_pagesubmit`) due to original Qualtrics export format.

License

See `LICENSE.txt` for details on data and code usage rights.

Code License: MIT License - Free to use and modify with attribution

Data License: CC BY 4.0 - Free to use with attribution

Contact Information

For questions about this replication package, please contact:

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Version History

- **v1.0** ([Nov 2025]): Initial release for journal publication

Last updated: April 2026